

PAKRD Nuclear Lexis Numeration Frame

(PAKRD System Specification & Protocol)

001 – 010 – Numerals

011 – 019 – Pronouns & Deictics

020 – “twenty” / “human”

021 – 039 – Body Parts

040 – 059 – Kinship Terms

060 – 079 – Core Verbs

080 – 099 – Fauna & Natural Phenomena

100 – 119 – Household Items & Artifacts